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“BEYOND SUCCESS: THE UNTOLD STORY OF A BREADWINNER”

When we were born, it's like life gave us a glimpse of hope, the hope to rise above the struggles we came from. Growing up, I often heard stories and testimonies of people who dreamed of escaping poverty. I saw it all around me. But as I walked through my own journey, I realized that some of us are destined to carry the bigger responsibility, to become the breadwinner of the family. I started building myself early. I prayed constantly that whatever challenges came my way, I could handle them, especially knowing that my parents couldn't give me everything I wished for. Unlike others, what I wanted didn't come easily. I had to work for every single thing I needed.

During high school, I would walk several kilometers just to attend classes. Sometimes, I stayed with my uncle to lessen expenses. Every step, every drop of sweat, every tear, every peso, and every little help I received—I treasured them deeply. After finishing high school, I honestly thought I couldn't go to college. But because of my perseverance and strong desire to help my family, I enrolled in a public school where tuition was affordable.

I've always been a person of initiative. Whenever the money given to me wasn't enough, I found ways to earn. My parents never knew that I took sideline jobs—hosting events, driving, selling, and doing whatever honest work I could find just to sustain my needs.

When I finally graduated, I was happy, but I knew my journey wasn't over. I told myself that as the family's breadwinner, I needed to pass the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) to secure a stable job. I couldn't afford to enroll in a prestigious review center, so I studied on my own, two to three hours every night. I believed that once I became licensed, I could start giving back to my parents. In 2015, after four months of self-review, God answered my prayers—I passed the LET. I still remember the moment I saw my name on the list. I was standing in front of a church, crying, saying, “Thank You, Lord, for this gift.” It was my offering to my parents who had sacrificed so much for me.

But life after passing the board exam wasn't easy. Getting into Department of Education (**DepEd**) required a long process like teaching demos, interviews, and waiting. Yet God was faithful. My boss encouraged me to apply for an Instructor position in a state college. It wasn't easy either passing through CHED's screening felt like going through the eye of a needle. But in 2017, I was officially hired as Instructor I. That was one of the happiest moments of my life. During my time as a job order employee, my salary was small, yet I still managed to save and support my family. When I finally received my first paycheck as a job order, I proudly gave everything to my parents. That feeling of being able to give back was priceless.

From then on, I found joy in sharing not only with my family but also with others even organizing my own foundation. However, being a breadwinner is not always easy. Many people think that once you have a stable job, life becomes comfortable. But they don't see the sacrifices behind every peso sent, every bill paid, every dream supported. Sometimes, we even forget our own needs because we always put others first. I've helped my siblings and supported others, too. Thankfully, two of them are now professionals and that's one of my greatest achievements. Yet, many breadwinners can relate when I say: behind every successful family is someone who silently sacrifices, working overtime, crying in silence, and giving up personal dreams just to make others' lives better. Sometimes, people never ask where the money came from or how hard it was earned. They don't see the nights of exhaustion, the sacrifices meant for ourselves but given to others instead. It's painful at times to see our efforts taken for granted, but we endure because of love.

To all breadwinners out there, I salute you. We should be proud of ourselves. Through time, I've learned that we also deserve to rest, to enjoy life, and to say no when needed. We should not only give but also teach others how to stand on their own and how to "catch a fish." As of today, I continue to embrace my role as a breadwinner, not as a burden, but as a blessing. It's a beautiful journey of love, sacrifice, and faith. And in every chapter of my life, I am reminded that beyond success lies the untold story of every breadwinner, a story of courage, resilience, and a heart that never stops giving.